

DCLXVI 2024: Call for papers

DCLXVI 2024 organizing and proceedings committees

31st July 2024

Abstract

The *International Workshop on Designing the Conceptual Landscape for a XAIR Validation Infrastructure* (DCLXVI 2024), organized by the Horizon Europe projects AI4Work and BatCAT, will be held on 11th December 2024 at RPTU Kaiserslautern, Germany. We are requesting manuscripts to be submitted by 19th October 2024. More information can be found on the workshop website (<https://batcat.info/dclxvi/>).

1 Vision statement

The rapid advancement of AI technologies necessitates the development of robust validation infrastructures and data documentation schemas to ensure that AI systems are transparent, reliable, and trustworthy. The DCLXVI 2024 International Workshop will survey the conceptual landscape of explainable-AI-ready (XAIR) models and data. The definition of core concepts relevant to data integrity, algorithmic transparency, and user interpretability will be explored.

Explainable AI (XAI) addresses the challenge of transparency by making AI systems' inner workings understandable. Ontologies permit documenting such an understanding, so that AI systems can supply explanations that are accurate, relevant, and understandable - by machines and by humans. There, semantic technology becomes necessary. One use case for this, among many, is retrieval-augmented generation applied to large language models, where semantic technology can contribute to ensuring that information is processed correctly in context. Such combinations of learning by induction and deduction will become essential to XAI systems for applications requiring precise, context-aware information, such as in safety-critical industrial environments. However, any successful metadata standardization effort for explainable-AI-readiness presupposes an exploration and critical discussion of the core concepts for documenting models and data such that they become XAIR.

At DCLXVI 2024, we will explore the potential of metadata standardization as well as conceptual analysis and engineering for AI validation at the state of the art of applied ontology and epistemology. Building XAIR digital infrastructures involves ensuring data privacy, addressing ethical concerns, and adhering to regulatory requirements. Standardization is highly relevant to international regulatory efforts, *e.g.*, the introduction of digital product passports. DCLXVI 2024 will investigate the prerequisites at a conceptual level for developing and documenting AI systems that are not only technically robust but also transparent, interpretable, and trustworthy.

2 Paper categories and scope of the workshop

Manuscript submission and reviewing are done through EasyChair.¹ Submit your manuscript by 19th October 2024 and, if accepted, the camera-ready files by 30th November 2024. The proceedings will be published in the Springer series Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems (LNNS), and by the camera-ready stage latest, manuscripts must conform with the specifications for publication in that series. Upon submission, select the appropriate category for your manuscript:

1. *Discussion of a core concept for XAI-readiness*; if you select this, your paper *must include*² a discussion of literature definitions of a concept relevant to XAI-readiness.
2. *Surveying the landscape of multiple core concepts*; if you select this, your paper *must include* an analysis of how or whether different definitions of concepts relevant to XAI-readiness can be combined with each other.
3. *Applied ontology techniques for visualizing or designing the conceptual landscape*; if you select this, your paper *must include* an application of said techniques to part of the conceptual landscape relevant to XAI-readiness.
4. *Going beyond FAIR - what is insufficient about the FAIR principles?* If you select this, your paper *must include* a discussion of requirements that are insufficiently addressed by the FAIR principles.

3 What are the XAIR core concepts?

Core concepts for XAI-readiness (*i.e.*, the concepts to be discussed at the workshop) can include the following:

- Explainability and explanation;
- reproducibility, reliability, and reliance;
- opacity and transparency, interpretability and interpretation;
- DIKW: Data, information, knowledge, and wisdom;
- responsibility, trust, trustworthiness and reasons/motivations for trusting;
- model design, parameterization, and optimization;
- holistic validation and unit testing (of models and simulation codes);
- theoretical virtues (of models);
- epistemic agents, vices, and virtues;
- the four elements of “FAIR,” possibly requiring a revision or update;
- simulation; applying and evaluating models;
- Context awareness, subject matter, and logical subtraction.

¹URL: <https://easychair.org/my/conference?conf=dclxvi2024>

²“Must include” means that part of the paper must be about this – not all of the paper.

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